

On the property of the Smarandache-Riemann zeta sequence

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Abstract In this paper, some elementary methods are used to study the property of the Smarandache-Riemann zeta sequence and obtain a general result.

Keywords Riemann zeta function, Smarandache-Riemann zeta sequence, positive integer.

§1. Introduction and result

For any complex number s , let

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k^{-s}$$

be the Riemann zeta function. For any positive integer n , let T_n be a positive real number such that

$$\zeta(2n) = \frac{\pi^{2n}}{T_n}, \tag{1}$$

where π is ratio of the circumference of a circle to its diameter. Then the sequence $T = \{T_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ is called the Smarandache-Riemann zeta sequence. About the elementary properties of the Smarandache-Riemann zeta sequence, some scholars have studied it, and got some useful results. For example, in [2], Murthy believed that T_n is a sequence of integers. Meanwhile, he proposed the following conjecture:

Conjecture. No two terms of T_n are relatively prime.

In [3], Le Maohua proved some interesting results. That is, if

$$\text{ord}(2, (2n)!) < 2n - 2,$$

where $\text{ord}(2, (2n)!)$ denotes the order of prime 2 in $(2n)!$, then T_n is not an integer, and finally he defies Murthy's conjecture.

In reference [4], Li Jie proved that for any positive integer $n \geq 1$, we have the identity

$$\text{ord}(2, (2n)!) = \alpha_2(2n) \equiv \sum_{i=1}^{+\infty} \left[\frac{2n}{2^i} \right] = 2n - a(2n, 2),$$

where $[x]$ denotes the greatest integer not exceeding x .

So if $2n - a(2n, 2) < 2n - 2$, or $a(2n, 2) \geq 3$, then T_n is not an integer.

In fact, there exist infinite positive integers n such that $a(2n, 2) \geq 3$, and T_n is not an integer. From this, we know that Murthy's conjecture is not correct, because there exist infinite positive integers n such that T_n is not an integer.

In this paper, we use the elementary methods to study another property of the Smarandache-Riemann zeta sequence, and give a general result for it. That is, we shall prove the following conclusion:

Theorem. If T_n are positive integers, then 3 divides T_n , more generally, if $n = 2k$, then 5 divides T_n ; If $n = 3k$, then 7 divides T_n , where $k \neq 0$ is an integer.

So from this Theorem we may immediately get the following

Corollary. For any positive integers m and $n(m \neq n)$, if T_m and T_n are integers, then

$$(T_m, T_n) \geq 3, \quad (T_{2m}, T_{2n}) \geq 15, \quad (T_{3m}, T_{3n}) \geq 21.$$

§2. Proof of the theorem

In this section, we shall complete the proof of our theorem. First we need two simple Lemmas which we state as follows:

Lemma 1. If n is a positive integer, then we have

$$\zeta(2n) = (-1)^{n+1} \frac{(2\pi)^{2n} B_{2n}}{2(2n)!}, \quad (2)$$

where B_{2n} is the Bernoulli number.

Proof. See reference [1].

Lemma 2. For any positive integer n , we have

$$B_{2n} = I_n - \sum_{p-1|2n} \frac{1}{p}, \quad (3)$$

where I_n is an integer and the sum is over all primes p such that $p - 1$ divides $2n$.

Proof. See reference [3].

Lemma 3. For any positive integer n , we have

$$T_n = \frac{(2n)!b_n}{2^{2n-1}a_n}, \quad (4)$$

where a_n and b_n are coprime positive integers satisfying $2||b_n, 3|b_n, n \geq 1$.

Proof. It is a fact that

$$\zeta(2n) = (-1)^{n-1} \frac{2^{2n-1} \pi^{2n}}{(2n)!} \cdot B_{2n}, \quad n \geq 1, \quad (5)$$

where

$$B_{2n} = (-1)^{n-1} \frac{a_n}{b_n}, \quad n \geq 1. \quad (6)$$

Using (1), (5) and (6), we get (4).

Now we use above Lemmas to complete the proof of our theorem.

For any positive integer n , from (4) we can directly obtain that if T_n is an integer, then 3 divides T_n , since $(a_n, b_n) = 1$.

From (1), (2) and (3) we have the following equality

$$\zeta(2n) = \frac{\pi^{2n}}{T_n} = (-1)^{n+1} \frac{(2\pi)^{2n} B_{2n}}{2(2n)!} = (-1)^{n+1} \frac{(2\pi)^{2n}}{2(2n)!} \cdot \left(I_n - \sum_{p-1|2n} \frac{1}{p} \right),$$

Let

$$\prod_{p-1|2n} p = p_1 p_2 \cdots p_s,$$

where $p_i (1 \leq i \leq s)$ is a prime number, and $p_1 < p_2 < \cdots < p_s$.

Then from the above, we have

$$\begin{aligned} T_n &= \frac{(-1)^{n+1} \cdot \pi^{2n}}{\frac{(2\pi)^{2n}}{2(2n)!} \cdot \left(I_n - \sum_{p-1|2n} \frac{1}{p} \right)} = \frac{(-1)^{n+1} \cdot (2n)!}{2^{2n-1} \cdot \left(I_n - \sum_{p-1|2n} \frac{1}{p} \right)} \tag{7} \\ &= \frac{(-1)^{n+1} \cdot (2n)! \cdot \prod_{p-1|2n} p}{2^{2n-1} \cdot \left(I_n \cdot \prod_{p-1|2n} p - \prod_{p-1|2n} p \cdot \sum_{p-1|2n} \frac{1}{p} \right)} \\ &= \frac{(-1)^{n+1} \cdot (2n)! \cdot p_1 p_2 \cdots p_s}{2^{2n-1} \cdot \left(I_n \cdot p_1 p_2 \cdots p_s - p_1 p_2 \cdots p_s \cdot \left(\frac{1}{p_1} + \frac{1}{p_2} + \cdots + \frac{1}{p_s} \right) \right)} \\ &= \frac{(-1)^{n+1} \cdot (2n)! \cdot p_1 p_2 \cdots p_s}{2^{2n-1} \cdot (I_n \cdot p_1 p_2 \cdots p_s - p_2 p_3 \cdots p_s - p_1 p_3 \cdots p_s - \cdots - p_1 p_2 \cdots p_{s-1})} \end{aligned}$$

Then we find that if $p_i | p_1 p_2 \cdots p_s, 1 \leq i \leq s$, but

$$p_i \nmid (I_n \cdot p_1 p_2 \cdots p_s - p_2 p_3 \cdots p_s - p_1 p_3 \cdots p_s - \cdots - p_1 p_2 \cdots p_{s-1}).$$

So we can easily deduce that if T_n are integers, when $n = 2k, 5$ can divide T_n ; While $n = 3k$, then 7 can divide T_n .

This completes the proof of Theorem.

References

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